

A Study about the Happiness Level of Women in India

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“Women have a vital role in environmental management and development.

Their full participation is therefore essential to achieve sustainable development”

- Principle 20, Rio Declaration

Sustainable development is “development which meets the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs” (Brundtland Report, 1987). It therefore includes the needs of both women and men. Women are key the agents for development. They play an important role in achieving sustainable development of a country. Happiness level of a people in a country can well be correlated with a countries development. Happiness is considered as an important tool to frame public policies and it also helps to measure the effectiveness of it. UN World Happiness Report of 2018 has stated that Finland ranks number one in Happiness level and India is in 133rd position out of 156 countries. If we take Nordic countries, almost all the countries ranks in first positions. So a society with happy people are very important for a countries Economic development. This paper aims to find out happiness level of women in India in selected years. The major objectives of the study are examining the happiness level of women in India on different aspects like Women Health, Education and Work. The study uses only the secondary data to find out the happiness level of women with respect to their health, education and work.

Keywords: Happiness Level, Sustainable Development, Public Policies, Economic Development, Health and Education.

Introduction

According to Economist Carol Graham,” happiness is satisfaction of life in general”. Often it is termed as subjective wellbeing (Happiness around the world). Happiness is what everyone desire to feel. Studies show that there is a link between happiness and development of a country. No country can progress without the

development of women in their country since they constitute half of the population and they play a crucial role in sustainable development of a country. The development of an economy can be correlated with the happiness level of the people in a country. In this aspect, women happiness plays a very important role and their happiness level can be linked with the growth and development of a country. The happiness level of women is very important because many Nordic countries have proved that people's happiness definitely can be correlated with the growth of an economy.

Literature Review

Stevenson and Wolfers(2009) in their article “ Paradox of Declining Female Happiness” found that although the lives of the women in the United States improved by several measures during the period 1972 to 2006, their happiness level has been decreased to a greater level. They also identified a wide happiness level inequality in US. Happiness from their point view does not increase with rising incomes of the country. In their study Stevenson and Wolfers pointed out many factors that may be the reason for decline of happiness of women relative to men.

Jeffrey D.Sachs (2016)in his article “Happiness and Sustainable development “clearly explained the concepts related to sustainable development and how happiness can be an important factor that determines sustainable development. In this article he points out the importance of measuring happiness. The article states that sustainable development and wellbeing or the satisfaction of the individual about their life situations are closely related.

Objectives of the Study

- To examine the happiness level of women in India.
- To study the happiness level of women with respect to their job.
- To examine the happiness level of women with respect to their health in India.
- To compare the happiness level of educated and uneducated women in India.
- To arrive at relevant findings and conclusion.

Methodology of the Study

The study focuses only on secondary data. The data has been taken from the World Value Survey (WVS) report during the year 2001, 2006 and 2012.

World Value Survey (WVS):A rigorous scientific method was employed for the study. The sample was designed to be representative of the entire population, i.e; 18 years and older. The survey was conducted in 18 states of India which covered almost 97% population. 40 districts in the country were identified for the purpose of the survey (a little less than 1/10th of the districts in the country). The 40 districts were spread across 18 states. Within each state, the districts in which the survey was to be conducted was selected by circular sampling (PPS: Probability Proportion to Size). Once all the 40 districts were selected, the Lok Sabha (Lower House of the Parliament) constituency that covered the districts was identified. If the sampled districts has more than one Lok Sabha constituency, the one which had larger proportion of the districts was selected. The number of the respondents to be interviewed in each state was determined on the basis of the state share in the national population (Probability Proportion to Size).

Significance of the Study

Happiness is crucial factor for policy making when it comes to sustainable development. Studying the happiness level of women is very important, since women play as a key driver in sustainable development of a country. Study about happiness level of women will help in framing effective policies and thereby improve the efficiency and then leads to economic development. This paper

tries to examine the happiness level of women in India during the year 2001 to 2012. The study further examined happiness level of women in different aspects like health, education and level of happiness in their job.

Women Happiness and Sustainable Development

When a country thinks about sustainable development, they definitely have to include the happiness level of the people. It is not mere, the GDP (gross domestic product) growth or their standard of living or per capita income but thereal growth or development lies with the happiness level of the people. When we talk about the happiness level of the people most importantly we have to include human happiness as it gives us the real growth of the country. According to Professor Jeffrey Sachs director of Centre for Sustainable development at Columbia University states that, happiness of individuals are the path to sustainable development and vice versa. He also observed that the list of the top ten countries closest to achieving the sustainable development goals mirrors a ranking of the world's happiest countries. Any country where women development is achieved, those countries face very well in Human Development Index (HDI), Per Capita Income and Social and Health Indicators. Countries like Norway, Sweden and Denmark are in the top positions in HDI mainly because the women in that country are developed. Hence for achieving sustainable development, women happiness level should be taken and that will give us whether an economy has attained real growth or not.

Happiness Level of Women in India

To study about the happiness level of women in India is very important because among the various indicators to find out the real growth of an economy, happiness level play a very important role. In this, women happiness level is very important as it has a very significant role to be played. Hence the data below will give us a picture about the general happiness level of women during the year 2001, 2006 and 2012.

Source: Computed from World Value Survey Report 2001, 2006 and 2012

Figure 1 represents the happiness level of women in India. This is taken once in six years. So from 2001 to 2012 the level of happiness level of women in India is depicted here. It can be understood from the diagram that women in general are happy over the years. From the diagram it is clear that the happiness level of women during the period 2001 and 2006 has been in the same level with 45.91 per cent whereas it has only slightly improved to 49.5 per cent during the year 2012. Even it shows that they are not very happy, the happiness level in general is definitely not very bad. Hence it can be inferred from the diagram that the happiness level women in India is satisfactory

Happiness Level in Health of Women in India

Health indicator is also considered to be a very important one. Healthy people are more productive for an economy. A good health will make people more cheerful and this brings happiness in their life. When we mention about healthy people, we have to take into consideration most importantly about women and their happiness level in their health.

Source: Computed from World Value Survey Report 2001, 2006 and 2012

From figure 2 it can be inferred that the level of happiness in health of women in India and how happy they are when it comes to their health. The performance over the year shows that the level of happiness has been good. From the diagram it is understood that during the year 2001, the level of happiness has been 42.4 per cent and that increased to 47.9 per cent during 2006. Whereas during the year 2012 it slightly reduced to 44.5 per cent. Even then the performance has been quite satisfactory and majority of the women have stated their happiness level is good.

Happiness Level in Job Satisfaction of Employed Women

Women who are employed must have job satisfaction. Their happiness level towards job satisfaction is very important. If women’s happiness level is higher in their job, more productive will be the working place. The percentage of employed women are increasing year after year in India. Hence it is very important to examine their level of happiness towards their job.

Figure 3 depicts the happiness level in job satisfaction of employed women in India. From this figure it is understood that the happiness level is only moderate. From the above figure it can be inferred that majority of the women are not happy with their job. The level of happiness is only moderate and near to 50 per cent of women are not happy with their job. Also the figure states that in the year 2001 it was 44.4 per cent and it has slightly declined to 41.7 per cent during the year 2012.

Source: Computed from World Value Survey Report 2001, 2006 and 2012

Happiness Level of Educated Women

Education plays a vital role in any economy. Happiness and education are strongly connected. Education contributes significantly to collective happiness. It is generally accepted that education improves people's lives in many aspects. The role played by educated women is very important. The happiness level of educated women must be examined to check whether women attaining the literacy level are happy or not. This study about educated women and their happiness level will help in understanding the importance of education in women's life and how it will improve their status in the society and how it leads to a country's economic development.

Source: Computed from World Value Survey Report 2001, 2006 and 2012

Figure 4 states about the happiness level of educated women. It can be understood from the diagram that the happiness level is quite satisfactory where 31.1 per cent in the year 2012 has responded that they are happy. Only 15.7 per cent in the same year have stated that they are very happy. So even though they are not very happy, some of the educated women feel that their level of happiness is better.

Happiness Level of Uneducated Women

It is also a must to know the happiness level of uneducated women. Since majority of the women in developing countries like India are uneducated and they are also contributing to economic development of the country. So it is essential to know whether uneducated women are also happy.

Source: Computed from World Value Survey Report 2001, 2006 and 2012

This is the diagrammatic figure for the happiness level of the uneducated women. This is shown in the figure 5. The uneducated women feel that they are very happy and 19.9 per cent of women in 2012 have responded like this. The percentage of women who have stated that they are very happy in fact has increased from 11.8 in 2006 to 19.9 per cent in 2012

Comparison of Happiness Level of Educated and Uneducated Women

Comparison of happiness level of educated and uneducated women is very essential to know the level of happiness among them.

Source: Computed from World Value Survey Report 2012

Figure 6 depicts the comparison of happiness level of educated and uneducated women in India. From the diagram it is understood that educated women are happy than uneducated women. A majority of 31.1 per cent of the educated women are happy than 18.4 per cent of uneducated women. Hence it can be inferred from the diagram that majority of 46 per cent of the educated feel they are happy than the uneducated women in India

Findings of the Study

- The general happiness level of women in India has been satisfactory. Majority of the women say around 49.5 per cent feel that they are happy.
- From the study, the finding is that from 45.9 per cent of women who feel their happiness level is good, it has increased to 49.5 per cent during the year 2012.
- Happiness level of women with respect to their health also shows a satisfactory performance as far as the study is concerned. A majority of 44.5 per cent of the women have stated that they feel happy about their health. Even though their observed a slight decrease from 47.9 per cent in 2006 to 44.5 per cent during 2012.
- From the study it can be inferred that the happiness level in job satisfaction of the employed women is only moderate. A majority of 41.7 per cent of women are not so happy when it comes to their job. Although from the study, the data shows that from 44.4 per cent it has declined to 41.7 per cent of women who have stated that their level of happiness with respect to job satisfaction is only moderate. It means that they are not very happy about their working condition.
- Findings of the happiness level of educated and uneducated women also differs. The level of happiness of educated women is that the majority of 31.1 per cent of women feel happy. Whereas around 19.9 per cent of the women who are uneducated feel that they are very happy and 18.4 per cent of women feel happy.
- Hence when we compare the educated and uneducated women, it is understood that educated women are happier than uneducated women.

Conclusion

To achieve sustainable development is the main goal for many countries. Especially it is a challenge for developing countries like India to reach the goal of Sustainable development. A significant role played by women is also very important. When we talk about the role of the women, one issue which needs to be stressed upon is their level of happiness. Some developed countries have achieved well with respect to the level of happiness of women and a country's development. Hence this study tries to portray about how happy Indian women are with respect to their job satisfaction, their health and about happiness level of educated and uneducated women. The study shows that the level of happiness in India is satisfactory even though it varies when it comes to educated and uneducated women. It can be concluded that happiness level should be taken as an important indicator for an economic growth.

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